

Together and Apart in the Time of Study: Teaching, Learning, Listening in Online Courses (An Application of the Technology of Difference)

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Mas las sirenas tienen un arma mucho mas terrible que su canto, esto es, su silencio.

—Franz Kafka, "El Silencio de las Sirenas"¹

Learning Together and Apart in the Time of Study

Heidegger has been the principle source of my attempt to understand how and why listening is at the center of teaching. For me a key moment in Heidegger's work occurs when he is speaking to the students at Freiberg University upon returning to the seminar room for the first time since his infamous and inglorious departure and subsequent ban from teaching. In the first of the lectures that would later be published as a volume under the title *What is Called Thinking?* (1968) Heidegger sets the agenda for the course of study: he and his students are there, together, "attempting to learn thinking. We are all on the way together" (p. 14). I will come back to this 'togetherness,' and to what it means to be both included in and excluded from the 'we' who are on the way together. First, however, a few more words on Heidegger's setting of the agenda for the seminar where they are attempting to learn thinking.

In setting this agenda Heidegger draws our attention to the condition of listening as necessary for all who are participating in the seminar, but especially for the teacher, who is guiding the group as they undertake this difficult challenge of learning thinking. If they are going to learn thinking, which sounds like a process and also a language, but which is, of course, an ontology or a way of being, or what Foucault (1984) called an 'attitude,' they must first learn to become aware of what is addressing them *essentially*. In other words, they must learn to learn, because "to learn means to make everything we do answer to whatever essentials address themselves to us *at a given time*" (Heidegger, 1968, p. 14; my emphasis). Here, the time that is "given" is the time when that which is *essential* is unfolding or presenting itself to us.

What stands out for me as significant is the identification of a particular kind of time, or, put more succinctly, the discovery of a temporal horizon, a unique place marked by a unique time, where we learn thinking. Through my work on Arendt (Duarte, 2010b), I have explored this unique time of learning as a time of radical possibility, or as the temporality of *kairos* when the linear flow of time, *kronos*, is interrupted by an opening that allows something wholly different to emerge. Learning happens when we find ourselves in that unique time of possibility, and by discovering ourselves there, perhaps

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unexpectedly, we find ourselves ready to receive the address of the essential.² Learning has its own temporality, and in this paper I want to indicate how listening operates as a way of perceiving that unique time, and, in turn, of cultivating and/or maintaining it (to the extent this is ever possible!).

Teachers learn to listen closely in order to ‘teach’ their students to learn thinking. Both kinds of learning happen in a specific time and through a specific practice. Indeed, learning involves ‘discovering’ oneself in that time when the essential is addressing us, or when we find ourselves engaged in what Tyson Lewis (2011; 2013), following Agamben, calls study. In study, as Agamben (1995) in concert with Heidegger might say, we are taken up by the address of the essential, ‘stupefied’ by the questions that present themselves to us. For Heidegger, learning thinking follows from the recognition that we are on our way, and that we are not yet thinking. For Agamben, study is the recognition of our potentiality, which is an ontology of both possibility—or natality, to use Arendt’s (1977) language—and impossibility, or what Heidegger (1995) would call the withdrawal of presencing into *das nichts* (the nothing). Study is the play of potentiality, the feeling of power or plentitude (as Nietzsche might put it; cf. Heidegger, 1991) co-arising with the feeling of weakness or impotency (as Socrates appears to have experienced³). “*Most thought provoking is that we are not yet thinking*” (Heidegger, 1968, p. 4, emphasis in original) is Heidegger’s mantra for study, where, in being stupefied, we recognize our inability to think (properly), and yet from this recognition we are spurred on the way of learning. Learning thinking happens in study. As Agamben (1995) puts it, “Studying and stupefying are in this sense akin: those who study are in the situation of people who have received a shock and are stupefied by what has struck them, unable to grasp it and at the same time powerless to leave hold” (p. 64). Teachers learning to listen closely are caught up in the process of their students’ learning. They are absorbed in letting their students learn, and in this sense are studying their learning. Learning to listen closely is the ongoing study of their students’ learning. (Phrasing here is important: learning to listen closely expresses the play of potentiality [possibility/impossibility, potency/impotence]).

Learning depends, as Heidegger (1968) puts it, on “the presence of some teacher who can make the apprentice comprehend” (p. 15) the address of the essential. What this suggests is that teachers, in learning to listen closely, are already located in the time of study.

Teaching, *as a form of study*, is *occurring* ‘ahead,’ which here means *further forward in time*, but not in the sense of being more experienced, and thus more ‘advanced.’ Rather, the teacher is ‘ahead’ in the sense of dwelling or being *in* that time where the essential is presenting itself: “The teacher is ahead of his apprentices in this alone, that he has still far more to learn than they—he has to learn to let them learn” (Heidegger, 1968, p. 15). To be ‘ahead’ is thus to be (more caught up, entangled) in the time of learning. The challenge or difficulty of teaching is that the teacher *must remain* both *with* and *apart from* the students. Learning is a process, or *way*, that the teacher and students are in-and-on *together*. Yet, the teacher is always ‘ahead’ of the students, and thus *apart* from them

because he still always has *more* to learn than they do: “The teacher must be capable of being more teachable than the apprentices” (Heidegger, 1968, p. 15).⁴

While it seems clear that the capacity of being more teachable implies that the teacher dwells in ‘the near future,’ always projected into the time of possibility, natality, ‘ahead’ of the students, where learning happens, it is not clear who or what is ‘throwing’ the teacher ahead into the time of study. If the learning of the students “depends obviously on the presence of some teacher,” does it follow that the learning of the teacher, the one who “has still far more to learn than they,” also depends on the presence of one who can make him comprehend, can turn him towards the address of the essential? And if it does, who or what is this ‘teacher’ who teaches the teacher?

It is my conjecture that it is the students themselves who re-present this *turning back* of the teacher (in the sense of turning him away from them, pushing him apart), and who, in this re-presentation, teach the teacher to be teachable by projecting him into ‘the near future,’ the time of learning and study. If the teacher must learn to let the students learn, then this learning happens when the students teach him to remain silent. The projection of the teacher into the near future is a re-turning of the teacher to the place of study, where he must remain apart yet together with the students whom he must continue to study. Teaching in this way is the silent contemplation of the students’ learning. Being a teacher in this sense depends on the capacity of the teacher to receive this teaching. And this capacity is a form of receptivity, or close listening, that enables the teacher to remain in the place of study, steadfast in the ‘draft,’ as Heidegger describes the place where Socrates stood.⁵ In the remainder of this paper, I would like to share how I came to ‘discover’ this way of teaching by undergoing the experience of being thrown by my students when I unexpectedly ‘heard’ my students ignoring me, or listened to their silence in response to my professorial voice. But first, I’d like to make an excursus on silence.

An Excursus on Silence

How does one ‘hear’ silence? Recalling the composer John Cage, one is tempted to respond, by listening to it being performed. Can one *perform* silence, in the sense of enacting it or making it, as in the performance of Cage’s groundbreaking piece *4’33”*? As I will discuss in my next section, I learned to hear silence by encountering my students’ performance of silence. I encountered the active production of silence in the learning space, and thereby learned how to listen to it. What does it mean to listen to silence, and why is this so important for educators? And why might the online learning context be one where educators can learn to listen to silence? The last question will be taken up in my next section. Here I want to turn to the work of Luce Irigaray, who not only emphasizes the centrality of listening in teaching, but also, like Heidegger, identifies silence as a human phenomenon (production) that must be cultivated in the learning context as a way of affirming the singularity of each person who is present. With this affirmation teachers take up what we might call, after Arendt, the conservation of natality and plurality. For Irigaray, listening is not only the result of silence, in the sense of ‘not speaking,’ but the result of a silence that is both always present and always being produced. Listening is the perception of this *already existing* and *always unfolding*

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silence. In turn, ‘hearing’ silence requires that we perceive it. Yet, this requirement demands new forms of perception, which emerge when we heed what Irigaray (2008) identifies as the imperative to construct an alternative logic.

In her essay “Listening, Thinking, Teaching” (2008), Irigaray insists that as educators, “we have no alternative but to invent another logic” (p. 238). For her, this is the most urgent project for educators, who have no choice but to lead the way in making a path toward a philosophical horizon where the teachings of western and eastern philosophy can appear both side by side and in relation to one another. Writing in a way that is close to Heidegger’s writing, Irigaray (2008) says, “The problem for us, as Westerners, is that it is no longer a question of mastery, but one in which we have now to let be done as well as to do, to let be as well as to be. We then imperceptibly enter another logic, another culture” (p. 232). If listening is the manner through which we move into this ‘other’ culture, then the movement we make into this ‘new’ horizon happens as we perceive what Heidegger calls “the inner essence of ‘logic’” itself (qtd. in Inwood, 1999, p. 22). This perception, which is a way of listening that Heidegger describes as the “speculative-hermeneutic experience of language,” is grounded in a more fundamental practice that he calls “sighetik [*die Sighetik*, the ‘art of silence,’ from the Greek *signan*, ‘to keep silent.’]” (qtd. in Inwood, 1999, p. 22).

The art of silence may be one way of describing the listening that is moving toward the other, and for Irigaray (2008), this is the educational form of listening, or the kind of listening that happens when teachers and students are not attempting to “[grasp] something in order to integrate and order it into [their] own world,” but are, rather, opening up their world “to something or someone external and strange to it. Listening-to is a way of opening ourselves to the other and of welcoming this other, its truth and its world as different from us, from ours” (p. 232). But such listening is always already made possible by the more fundamental presence of a silence that arises in-between teachers and students. The alterity appearing with listening-to is always dependent upon a gap or space that conserves the difference that mediates the experience of alterity, the strangeness of the new. The art of listening is thus what we might call a secondary art, because it proceeds from and/or is dependent upon the primary art of silence.

To speak of the ‘art of silence’ is evocative but also misleading, because the silence that mediates the fundamental difference between teachers and students is not one that is entirely ‘produced.’ This is why it is better to speak of ‘cultivation,’ which describes a process of dynamic interaction between what is ‘found’ and the gathering of this already existing. Silence is always already present, but once perceived as such, it needs to be protected, cared for, cultivated.

The art of silence is ultimately about maintaining the space for the proper reception of language. In turn, the productive activity of this art is first and foremost one of perceiving silence. For Irigaray, the art of silence is the conservational work that involves “the protection of a space, a place of silence” (Irigaray, 2001, p. 62). She calls this work conceiving silence.

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Irigaray writes, “to love each other between us ... requires the protection of a space, a place of silence.... The origin, if I can say this, of the love between us is silence” (Irigaray, 2001, p. 62). The conception of silence is less a speculation than a conservation or preservation of a space, a gap, where we can dwell together yet differently, free, in our singularity, in peace. Thus for Irigaray (2001), to conceive silence is to take up a way of teaching and learning “how to look at or listen to the other as subject” (p. 42).

As understood through Irigaray’s work, to teach and to learn are to cultivate a space that safeguards difference. This space, for Irigaray, is a place of silence, cultivated through perception, and preserved through a dwelling that remains radically tolerant. Perception is a way of relating on a deeply subjective and spiritual level, and for Irigaray, of safeguarding the becoming (growth and development) of each of us, separately and together. Perception is thereby a form of ‘letting’—“To leave the other to be, not to possess him in any way, to contemplate him as an irreducible presence, to relish him as an inappropriable good, to see him, to listen to him, to touch him, knowing that what I perceive is not mine” (Irigaray, 2001, p. 46).

Being Thrown by the Silence of Students

Heidegger (1968) writes, “if the relation between the teacher and the taught is genuine ... there is never a place in it for the authority of the know-it-all or the authoritative sway of the official” (p. 15). Within the pedagogy of *Gelassenheit* (letting-be) that I have been attempting to understand and practice, listening to one’s students is a key component. I have written on the need to take up a path of silence so as to open up the space for receptivity, for listening (Duarte, 2011, March). And it would seem to follow that this path enables one, in part, to avoid that authoritative modality that Heidegger identifies as having no place in teaching. But *the teacher must speak*. And so the question arises, how does one come to hear one’s own voice as expressing the ‘authoritative sway of the official’? How does one, as a teacher, learn how to listen to oneself, and to be capable of hearing when one takes up the position of the ‘know-it-all’?

These questions frame for me the focus of this paper, and also frame the kind of listening I have been learning when teaching online—taking up what we at Hofstra call distance learning, courses. Let me give a brief overview of the way I set up my distance learning courses, and then describe how I came to learn to listen to myself speaking in the voice of the authoritative official, the know-it-all, and why, as Heidegger indicated, there is no place for this voice once the students have arrived at the place of learning, and are dwelling in the time of study.

Indeed, *the teacher must speak*, and it is the necessity of speaking, or saying something edifying, evocative, provocative, and, in the end, thought-provoking, that was the primary motivation for me to accept the invitation to design and implement a set of distance learning courses. Over the years of teaching what we now call ‘traditional’ face-to-face courses, I enjoyed the freedom of spontaneity, of teaching ‘in the moment,’ and of attempting to keep it real and fresh each time I entered the classroom. My inspiration

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was, and continues to be, the genius of improvisational musicians, who, it seems to me, never play the same note or the same beat in the same way twice. While having its undeniable moments of euphoria, and one could even say ecstatic freedom, teaching improvisationally always happens in the *Jetzt-Zeit* (the now-time), and, as such, leaves behind only the memory of the event, the happening of learning, the performance, perhaps as a recording, and some notes taken by diligent students. But by design, the temporality of the improvisational learning event permits no repetition. While this can feel liberating, over time it produces a particular kind of novelty fatigue, where the expectation to always be ‘on’ is exhausting. Novelty fatigue also produces the desire to have a record of one’s teaching, and what I experienced was a kind of ‘rebound effect,’ or what Foucault (2005) describes as the “effects of the truth on the subject” (p. 16). The ‘truth’ of the practices of improvisational teaching rebounded to me, producing in me the desire not simply to *say something*, but to *record* this saying, or to say something that I could say again. Thus the desire for some kind of permanence in my teaching led me into the studios of Hofstra’s radio station where I host a weekly music show. And there, in WRHU’s studio north, I recorded ten lectures for my introduction to philosophy of education course, which examines the questions “What does it mean to be a philosophical educator? What does it mean to be educated by philosophy?”

The lectures are the starting point for my distance learning courses. My design of the course begins with the recording of the lectures. And the learning in the course begins with my students listening to these lectures. In terms of the process, I ask the students first to listen to my lecture, then to do the assigned reading, and then to participate in an online seminar that is mediated by VoiceThread (VT), a software program that allows students to leave written, audio, and video posts.

With some context now presented, I can return to questions about the ‘teachability’ of the teacher, and, specifically, how I came to learn to listen to myself speaking in the voice of the authoritative official, and was projected into the near future by my students.

The teacher must speak. And in my lectures, I spoke, mindful of the expectation I had for myself to say something I could ‘say again.’ Here, one might anticipate that I learned to hear myself speaking as the ‘know-it-all’ when I replayed and listened to my lectures during the course. But if this had happened, then I would only have been ‘hearing’ myself through myself, and been trapped in a solipsistic feedback loop. On the contrary, to become teachable requires that we learn to hear ourselves by listening to the way others hear us. So it was neither in listening to my lectures nor in reading the students’ responses to them that my teachability resided. Rather, it was in the VT seminar that I learned to hear myself as an official, embodying, insofar as one can be embodied in a distance learning class, the kind of official that has become normative in education today: the accountant who is monitoring the learning so as to insure that the projected outcomes are being met.

In describing to a colleague how I came to experience the rebound effect when I heard myself by hearing my students listen to and ignore me, I likened the experience to walking along the wide expanse of the sidewalk on Broadway in Manhattan, where small

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groups of people walking and talking are able to remain totally engaged and focused on a conversation while moving forward along the sidewalk at a steady pace, all the while weaving around others who are not part of their group. This is precisely how I felt as I attempted to enter into the online seminar space where my students were engaged in conversation about my lectures and readings. Despite my efforts to lead or steer the conversation in a particular direction—out of a desire to have them take up a particular section of the reading, or a question that I raised in lecture—my students moved along as a group, weaving around my posts as if they were part of a conversation that was moving in another direction. Indeed, as I told my colleague, after two consecutive weeks of posting comments that were ignored, I recognized that I was not entirely *together* with my students. Paradoxically, in their posts, my students referred directly to me when making a comment in response to my lecture, while ignoring the posts I made during the online seminar.

After the second week, I arrived at the conclusion, and decided to continue under its working hypothesis, that the authority I was granted by my students to organize and prompt the seminar did not permit me to participate in the seminar, which they reserved as *their* space of learning.

In essence, my students taught me to let them learn by remaining silent toward me. They moved together *around* my voice—a voice that expressed a kind of authoritative sway, in the sense of rule or control. By remaining silent toward this voice, they withheld recognition of my presence with them in their time of learning. And in listening to their silence I was compelled to understand that I wasn't excluded, but rather I had been placed elsewhere. I had been thrown into the near future, into the time of teaching when, in contrast to the time of learning, we let learning be learned by remaining apart from our students. Being *ahead*, our work involves cultivating and maintaining that gap, in time, that demarcates the ones who study from the ones who protect their right to do so.

“In Almost Absolute Silence”

In the foregoing I have suggested that within the context of distance learning a new kind of pedagogical relationship has been revealed to me, one that is much more consistent with the principles of education I have been working under in the past eighteen years of teaching at the university. The pedagogy of *Gelassenheit*, of letting learning be learned, had created what Foucault (2005) calls the ‘rebound effect’ (*le retour*) (p. 16). Indeed, the practice of letting my students learn on their own turned back on me, rebounding so that it was the students who were teaching me, who were letting me learn, and who were letting me be apart from and distinct from them. In granting me a *freedom from* a particular kind of power, they were enacting the principle of academic freedom.⁶ From its inception at the University of Bologna, this principle has always been generated from above and beyond by an external authority that grants the university *en toto* freedom from the intrusion of external authority (a strange paradox, for sure), but also from within, by the students who retain a kind of local authority over the teaching and learning practices within the university. The faculty, for their part, remain in control and have authority of

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scholarship, research, etc., and thus we have with academic freedom a kind of balance of power between students and faculty.

The pedagogy of *Gelassenheit* rebounded to me when, as I said above, my students taught me how to remain silent.⁷ It was a rebound effect because I had already been enacting a form of listening that was grounded on what I understood to be a generative silence. Here ‘rebound’ should be understood in the sense of a recovery and amplification of strength, as well as of value. The principle of ‘letting be’ was returned, and it empowered me to understand anew the pedagogy that unfolds from listening and the generative silence that this receptivity is grounded in.

What did this renewed understanding of listening and silence reveal to me?

In her book *I Love to You* (1996), Luce Irigaray takes us back to the originary question that has been present throughout this essay: as she puts it, “Let us begin with: how am I to listen to you?” (p. 115). This question is ‘originary’ because we must constantly raise it and reflect upon it. It is the ‘first’ question, so to speak, not only in the sense of where we begin, but in terms of an origin and ground for teaching. Irigaray’s response to this fundamental question echoes what she writes in “Listening, Thinking, Teaching” (2008), but also what Heidegger (1968) says in the first lecture of *What is Called Thinking?*—especially when he says that what is most thought provoking is that he and his student are *not yet* thinking. Thus, in response to the question “How am I to listen to you?” Irigaray (1996) says that the statement *I am listening to you* means “to listen to your words as something unique, irreducible, especially to my own, as something new, as yet unknown” (p. 116). For me, to understand the implications of the rebound effect, the empowerment received from the return of the pedagogy of letting be, it is necessary to think about listening as *both* grounded in a generative form of silence *and* generating a form of silence, one that is precisely that building/dwelling where the freedom of the student is conserved. Listening is the building/dwelling that conserves the space of thinking, being and becoming, and is the basis of a teaching that cultivates what we might describe as the conservatory of learning (see Duarte 2010a).

Here we gather new insights into what Irigaray (1996) is indicating when she writes of the need and the necessity to move into a new logic. *I am listening to you*, she writes, “requires a transition to a new dimension” (p. 116). But in order for this movement, process, transition to occur, we have to think in terms of what Heidegger calls “the inner essence of ‘logic’” itself. This position we take *towards* logic does not make a new logic, but rather allows us to form a different relation to logic itself. As I noted above, we perceive this ‘inner essence’ of logic through a “speculative-hermeneutic experience of language,” which is itself grounded in a more fundamental practice that Heidegger calls “sigetics.” However, for Irigaray, this art of silence is more radical in the sense that it is not an artistic practice (*poesis*), but the *artwork* of silence. This is why she insists that listening produces a silence that conserves possibility, that preserves the space for learning in the sense of protecting the place of the unknown, the unexpected, and the not yet. Learning happens *in* that time and place where improvisation, spontaneity, or what Arendt calls the revolutionary power of natality unfolds. *I am listening to you* means I,

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teacher, am receiving you, student, “as someone and something *I do not know yet*, on the basis of a freedom and an openness put aside for this moment. *I am listening to you*: I encourage something unexpected to emerge, some becoming, some growth, some new dawn, perhaps. *I am listening to you* prepares the way for the not-yet-coded, *for silence*, *for a space* for existence, initiative, free intentionality, and support for your becoming” (Irigaray, 1996, p. 116-117; emphasis mine).

The effect of the pedagogy of letting-be rebounding to me offered the possibility of taking up a new way of understanding listening by indicating a new way of relating to a logic of listening. The ‘old’ presumption that a generative silence allows for listening, and thus letting be, is reversed, and the ‘new’ presumption is that silence is generated by listening. However, if we follow Irigaray, this silence remains a kind of gift offered to the student(s) from the teacher, an offer to remain apart from them in the sense of not interfering with their learning by imposing a direction upon it, but yet remaining together with them in the sense of bearing witness to this learning, to their becoming. It is precisely the taking up of a phenomenological stance that Heidegger calls the speculative-hermeneutic experience of language in the sense that in listening to the student, the teacher, me, is listening to you, student(s), “as the revelation of a truth that has yet to manifest itself —yours and that of the world revealed through and by you. *I give you a silence* in which your future—and perhaps my own, but *with* you and not *as* you and *without* you—may emerge and lay its foundation” (Irigaray, 1996, p. 117).

How can a silence be ‘given’ to the students? How can listening indicate silence *as a place* that holds open the future? How is it that I, ‘teacher,’ can return the silence enacted by my students in a way that more powerfully enables them to learn how to learn?

Listening offers up a silence, and in doing so silence reveals itself as the *space-time* of learning. In this *topos* of learning the stress is laid on an ontology of *becoming*, and for Irigaray (1996), this implies that the silence offered by the teacher is given with “no a priori, no pre-established truth or ritual” (p. 117). Given the experience I have recounted in this essay, this giving of silence is an act of reciprocity. And because learning is an event that captures both ‘teachers’ and ‘students,’ it is appropriate to describe listening and the silence it offers an event of *inter*-subjectivity. This designation should not be misunderstood as somehow closing that essential gap which, for Irigaray, is necessary for there to be a listening that receives each and every appearance of language (in the existential sense) as unique, irreducible, new and yet unknown. However, we must recognize that, as Irigaray consistently emphasizes, listening happens *between* people. *Inter*-subjectivity designates both the place *and* process of learning via listening that offers up a silence.

Inter denotes first and foremost the topological character of the silence that appears from listening — learning *qua* listening as dwelling/building that appears as a *place*. *Inter* used in this sense of going to the roots (i.e., *into* the ground: both earth and ontological foundation) captures the topology of listening as an enactment of a *horizon*, an ontology of *being-there* in the sense of *Da-sein*. To think in this way is to recall the Old French roots of *inter*, *enterrer*, which is based on Latin *in* – ‘into’ + *terra* ‘earth.’⁸ Learning

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with-*in* silence is a way to describe the *culture* that is cultivated (the dynamic interaction between what is ‘found’ and its gathering) in a particular *field* of education. And ‘field’ should be understood here as a particular branch of study or sphere of activity or interest. In turn, I am indicating/inculcating learning with-*in* silence as a field within the philosophy of education. *Inter* also denotes the processural character of the silence that appears from listening. Here ‘inter-’ is the prefix that denotes ‘between,’ ‘among,’ but also suggests ‘mutuality’ and ‘reciprocity.’ Here the origin to be recalled is Old French *entre*, which evolved from the Latin *inter* ‘between, among.’ In this sense silence is *inter*-subjective because it appears between and among teachers and students, who should now all be designated under the common title of ‘learners,’ or those who are enacting *study*. Thus silence

is the condition.... It ... assumes that the already existing world, even in its philosophical or religious form, should not be considered complete, already revealed or made manifest.... [T]he world must not be sealed already, it must still be open, the future not determined by the past. (Irigaray, 1996, p. 117)

In sum, the silence that appears *from* listening is both a process and a place of learning. It is a *condition* both in the sense of a particular way of existence *of* and *for* human being *qua* learning, and in the sense of being a particular *location* (circumstance, atmosphere) of human existence in learning. And when we think of silence as a *condition* we remember that the *inter*-subjectivity of learning is, ultimately, dialogic. Indeed, our listening and the silence it offers conserves and cultivates the possibility of *saying* (speaking, writing, etc.). So, when we describe silence as a *condition* we recall the roots of ‘condition’ in the Old French *condicion* (noun), *condicionner* (verb), from Latin *condicio(n)* ‘agreement,’ from *condicere* ‘agree upon,’ from *con* ‘with’ + *dicere* ‘say.’ The condition of silence offers up the possibility of a *speculative-hermeneutic experience of language*. Indeed, if the ground of learning thinking (study) is cultivated by the ‘art of silence,’ then the fruit of this ground is dialogue. Put otherwise, learning/study is the dynamic dialectic of receptivity (listening, reading, etc.) and expressivity (saying, writing, etc.).

Conclusion: Learning to Listen Closely, Possibility/Impossibility of Teaching

In the Summary to and Transition from the first to the second lecture in *What is Called Thinking?* (1968), Heidegger identifies the three themes that concerned the first meeting of his course. Of those, the second is the relation between teaching and learning. When he takes up this relation during the summary and transition, Heidegger links learning thinking with the address of the essential. In learning thinking, he tells his students, they may or may not “attain relatedness to what is most thought-provoking” (Heidegger, 1968, p. 25). This, he says, is “altogether out of the hands of those who practice the craft of thinking” (p. 25). What *is* in their hands, however, is the preparatory work that happens by learning to listen closely. So we can and must, if we are to learn thinking and ready ourselves for the possibility of being related to what is most thought-provoking, learn to listen closely. And in this endeavor, teacher and students are together because “to learn listening ... is the common concern of student and teacher” (p. 25).

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However, with his concluding words on the second major theme of lecture one, Heidegger reminds his students that potential for failure is always close at hand. Indeed, because they are *learning* thinking, and, in that process, are learning to listen closely, they remain on the way, potential and im-potential thinkers and listeners. He tells them, “No one is to be blamed ... if he is not yet capable of listening” (Heidegger, 1968, p. 25). Put differently, when they dwell together and apart in the time(s) of study, they remain learners who may or may not attain the relatedness to the address of the essential, which, in the end, is not yet happening in the seminar, not yet happening in close examinations of text, ideas, or words, both written and spoken. Most thought-provoking is that we are *not yet* thinking, and the ‘not yet’ names the time of study as a time defined by the play of potentiality/impotentiality happening in between past and future.

As Heidegger suggests at the end of this part of the summary, because the learning of close listening is the common concern of student and teacher, the *res publica*, if you will, the commons or public sphere of learning where they dwell together, they also share in the being together in temporality that defines the studio of learning. And so, Heidegger reminds his students, they are together in the play of potentiality/impotentiality, together learning close listening. Further, because the teacher is ‘ahead’ of the students in maintaining the studio so they can learn, he is also apart from and ahead in the play of potentiality/impotentiality. “[Y]ou must concede,” he says to them, “that the teacher’s attempt may go wrong and that, where he happens not to go wrong, he must often resign himself to the fact that he can not lay before you in each instance all that should be stated” (Heidegger, 1968, pp. 25-26).

What Heidegger might have said, and what I hear as implied in what he is saying, is, first, that teaching is a play of right/wrong, success/failure, potentiality/impotentiality, and, second, that in the midst of this play, this dynamic, silences must be perceived and attended to. In fact, if learning thinking begins with learning to listen closely, then the silences must be anticipated, cultivated, and maintained. The teacher’s attempt to let learning happen may go wrong, and he may find himself impotent with regard to letting his students learn to listen closely. He may, as I discovered, overstep his boundaries, and speak too much, or with the voice of the know-it-all, and, thereby, reinstate the temporality of knowledge, the linear and chronological instrumental time. The silence that is heard in these occasions is the silencing of the students, and the closure of the space of study, the shutting down of the time of learning. The other silence that is heard, and one that the students must attend to, is the one that emerges in what cannot be said by the teacher.⁹

The teacher must speak. But, at times, his speaking does not communicate, and he remains impotent to engage students in learning to listen closely. In these cases we are reminded of the other sense of the teacher being apart from the students, or the apartness of the teacher and students. *The teacher must speak* but he cannot *say* all that needs to be said, because in teaching he remains related to the ‘not yet’ of study. He is offering his students something to listen to, to respond to, and in doing so he cannot say, nor should he attempt to say, all that needs to be said because there is still more to be said, most

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importantly, in response to what the students are saying. The 'not yet' bounds us to remain silent to the future response, and thus, the time of study is always in relation to the time that remains, the future arrival of the 'now moment,' which we must anticipate as the next time in the studio of learning. The silence of the teacher is thus also the silence of dwelling 'ahead' of his students, in the near future, where he waits for and anticipates their return, waiting upon their responses, listening closely to their learning.¹⁰

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Notes

¹ Franz Kafka, "El Silencio de las Sirenas" (1984), p. 11. "The Sirens have a still more fatal weapon than their song, namely their silence." These words from Kafka's meditation provide a perfect marquee announcement for this paper, calling our attention, as they do, to a moment in ancient mythology where the man of cunning, Odysseus, is confronted with yet another fateful challenge. I'm tempted to describe the teacher persona I perform as a spiritual descendant of Odysseus, navigating the complex and sometime treacherous waters of academia. But in this case, with Kafka, I'm reminded that the most 'awful weapon' I face is the silence that emerges in the learning space. The power of those silences manifests when one ignores or underestimates their threat, which is always a present danger of dismantling the authority of the one who speaks too much. To pay heed to the silences, to be attentive to them, is to remain humble in the face of the task at hand, which is to teach by letting learning happen, and thereby to open up a way into the time of study. The threat from the silence of study is always a potential to silence the voice of authority that interrupts and disrupts the freedom of study.

² Here it is important to note that this exceptional time, which I argue is one of the conditions necessary for the learning event to happen, is a temporal horizon. In turn, the educator cannot 'stage' but can only indicate or point to through what I will be exploring in this paper, following Heidegger, as a pedagogy of letting. Now, insofar as this pedagogy is possible at all, and specifically in the online educational platform, the actuality of this possibility is always dependent on the desire and willingness, no less than the capability, of an educator to take the *risk* of stepping-back and letting learning be. And this *risk* is happening in the 'ethical sphere' insofar as it grounded in unspoken trust, a leap of faith in the students to undertake learning in the horizon that has been signaled to them. And with this clarification I am registering a strong note of dissent against Dreyfus' (2002) Kierkegaardian critique of online education, a critique which contends that the ethical sphere cannot be 'simulated,' and thus the crucial 'risk taking' allowed and supported by authentic (*face-to-face, embodied*) education is absent from inauthentic (*virtual, online*) education.

³ I explore Socrates' 'impotence' in my essay "Kant, the Nomad, and the Publicity of Thinking: Finding a Cure for Socrates' Narration Sickness" (Duarte, 2009).

⁴ This 'being ahead' is one of the most persistent and consistent ways that Heidegger explores being through a temporality that is qualified as movement. From this early lecture in 1924, published bilingually as *The Concept of Time* (1992), through *Being and Time* (1962), and, subsequently, *On Time and Being* (1972), Heidegger maintained that exploring the question of the meaning of being, or fundamental thinking, was a matter of a *way* and of *how* (*Wie*) that entangled us in what I call the strange present (*present extraño*), which is that temporal horizon where, first, we can experience the simultaneity of multiple traditions, or heritages, and, second, we 'leap ahead' into the 'original past.'

My project of originary thinking is an attempt to take up this strange present through a set of pedagogical protocols, as well as through experimental forms of writing. My book *Being and Learning* (Duarte, 2012a) is an extended example of thinking in the strange present.

⁵“All through his life and right into his death, Socrates did nothing else than place himself into this draft, this current, and maintain himself in it. This is why he is the purest thinker of the West. This is why he wrote nothing. For anyone who begins to write out of thoughtfulness must inevitably be like those people who run to seek refuge from any draft too strong for them” (Heidegger, 1968, p. 17). I’d like to examine how Socrates’ steadfastness, specifically his withholding of writing, is an example of study in the form of teaching. In not writing, Socrates stood in the midst of the play of potentiality/impotentiality.

⁶I have written a paper that explores the origins of academic freedom in medieval Bologna, and the implications of thinking that history (Duarte 2012b). The paper focuses, in part, on The *Habita*: the first or originary right granted to the university, articulated in the “imperial constitution” of 1158, at the Diet of Raoncaglia, willed by Frederick Barbarossa, and granted to the students and faculty of the university of Bologna. As cited in Compayré (1893): “We will ... that the students, and above all, the professors of divine and sacred laws, may be able to establish themselves and dwell in entire security in the cities where the study of letters is practiced. It is fitting that we should shelter them from all harm. Who would not have compassion on these men who exile themselves through love of learning, who expose themselves to a thousand dangers, and who, far from their kindred and their families, remain defenseless among persons who are sometimes of the vilest?” (p. 11).

⁷If we follow Foucault’s insights, the rebound effect is an important and dare I say ‘measurable outcome’ of the teaching and learning happening via a pedagogy of *Gelassenheit*. This paper is an attempt to indicate a possible set of terms for describing a way of assessing the learning. However, what can’t be emphasized enough here is that the one learning in this case is the teacher. If the rebound effect is registered as an occurrence of learning, then it is the teacher that we are focused on. There is some movement to account for the teacher *as* learner (e.g., the Teacher Education Accreditation Council [TEAC] Quality Principles for Teacher Education Programs (2010) identifies as the first of its ‘cross-cutting themes’ “learning how to learn”). But this remains a marginal notion in a time when ‘learner’ is almost everywhere designated as ‘student,’ which designation is, in turn, always assigned in contrast to ‘teacher.’ Lost in this logic is the sense that learning is a process that does not flow from a fixed subject position (teacher). In the dialogue published as “Conversations Along a Country Path,” Heidegger does well to describe and document this pre-subjective learning process as always already taking hold of us. This work, along with two other conversations, is published as volume 77 of Heidegger’s complete works (*Gesamtausgabe*) in German, and in English as *Country Path Conversations* (Heidegger, 2010). In this dialogue, *Gelassenheit* is presented as the composure, calmness and repose of an en-opened

thinking, but also as the en-opening of that thinking. Put differently, if *Gelassenheit* means something like the result of the pre-subjective process of 'having been released into the open/openness,' then letting (*lassen*) is the *way* we might subjectively indicate this pre-subjective process.

⁸Here it is difficult not to think of Arendt's (1998) claim that "the earth is the very quintessence of the human condition, and earthly nature, for all we know, may be unique in the universe in providing human beings with a habitat in which they can move and breathe without effort and without artifice" (p. 2).

⁹After reading an early draft of this paper, Tyson Lewis called my attention to a relevant section in Heidegger's *Being and Time* (1962), writing, "have you thought of connecting your comments on listening to Heidegger's ontological analysis of silence in *Being and Time*? In his analysis of the existential constitute of the 'there,' H. argues that 'reticence articulates the intelligibility of *Dasein* in so primordial a manner that it gives rise to a potentiality-for-hearing which is genuine, and to a being-with-one-another which is transparent' (Heidegger, 1962, p. 165). Here I am reading reticence as a kind of privation of language—a privation in the sense that it speaks equally to the capability to and not to speak. It is this im-potentiality of silence (an activity that is also an inactivity) that enables us to have a community." In my response to Lewis I wrote, "thanks for your *Being and Time* citation, which, yes, connects to what I'm exploring in this paper. 'Reticence' seems to relate to with-holding, or the decision to 'not speak', but also being thrown into silence. In either case, what arises is the potential for hearing, which, as you suggest, creates the conditions for the possibility of a community, or, in the case of our field of interest, a learning community. And this raises some questions with respect to the positionality of the teacher in relation to the community, specifically, how the power of the teacher's 'voice' is rendered 'moot,' or to play on the phonetics (here a double pun?), the teacher's voice is rendered 'mute.' In this sense, the teacher (as authoritative know it all) is 'deprived' of voice, and, as you suggest, the reticence he undergoes is a kind of privation. I suppose my point is, in part, to show how the community of learning must (I insist!) be a gathering of equals (in terms of Ranciere's (1991) sense of equality of intelligence). And thus, the emphasis on the teacher being first and foremost one who listens, and whose listening ultimately conserves (in the Arendtian sense) the space for learning. So, like Ranciere puts it, the teacher retains the responsibility that learning is happening. Might we say that the teacher is thus 'more' deprived of voice? (this would be a radical suggestion, for sure, given that the teacher must speak!)" Email correspondence, March, 2012.

¹⁰The experimental research documented and explored in this paper, as well as the opportunity to take up some of the initial findings with colleagues in the 2013 Orrs Island Philosophy of Education Summer Institute, is made possible in large part by a Hofstra University Provost Diversity Initiative grant. This paper is the first published account of the project *A Chance for a New Human Togetherness: "The Technology of Difference: Thinking Multi-culturally."* The aim of this project is to invite scholars, faculty and students into the process of creating new understandings of self and others through an

Irigaray-/Heidegger-inspired phenomenology of difference. Difference is a reverential phenomenon that provides a ground for our being together. In turn, what is unfolding here is thinking as a way of being, an ontology of receptivity and affirmation of diversity, a letting-be (*Gelassenheit*), without discrimination or judgment, of the plurality that appears before and beyond us. The *techne* of this phenomenology is a *technology of difference*, which, in the words of Irigaray (2008), arises through “a logic of coexistence in difference” (p. 237). Further, it implies a pedagogical initiative: “the most important thing we have to learn and teach is: how to communicate in difference.... And this is a crucial step for reaching another logic and entering into multiculturalism”(Irigaray, 2008, p. 237).